

PROPOSITIONAL-FRAME ANALYSIS OF THE WORD-FORMATION NEST WITH THE TOP ‘ΝΟΣΟΣ’ (DISEASE) IN ANCIENT GREEK

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Abstract: *The article is written in the framework of the study of the propositional-frame structure of the concept “DISEASE” in the ancient Greek language. The basic name of the concept, recorded in the ancient Greek language in the form of a word-formation nest with the top νόσος was analyzed. The main methodological approach is cognitive modeling of derivatives, in particular, modeling of a lexical-word-forming nest with the semantics of “disease” as a frame. The units of the metalanguage of description are such terms and related concepts as frame, slot, propositional scheme and proposition, which, on the one hand, reflect the most general form of verbalization of knowledge, and on the other hand, represent as clearly as possible various ways of semantic derivation and nomination of derived words. It is derived words that provide an adequate description of those types of knowledge that a person relies on when forming derivatives; at the same time, this knowledge creates the most important information for a person as a representative of a specific cultural environment and society. Based on dictionary data and original ancient Greek texts, 51 lexemes formed on the basis of the noun νόσος “disease” were identified. The mentioned word-formation nest is represented by different parts of speech, including nouns, adjectives, verbs and adverbs belonging to different chronological sections and formed by prefixation (4 lexemes), suffixation (29 lexemes) and stemming (18 lexemes). The analysis made it possible to identify in the frame model of the aforementioned nest a deep level of abstraction represented by 7 slots (lack of health, intensity, soreness, pathological state of the organ, causation, eliminating disease, and diagnosis), which are based on the corresponding propositional schemes and propositions.*

Keywords: *frame, proposition, word-formation nest, propositional scheme, ancient Greek, the DISEASE concept*

Introduction. In recent years, linguistics has gained significant insights from numerous studies that adopt a cognitive approach to understanding linguistic phenomena. This approach has introduced a new conceptual framework, where one of the key elements is the idea of

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‘structured mental representations’¹. These representations can be described as “the basic units of consciousness, components of the “collective unconscious,” the operational semantic units of memory, the “brick” of the conceptual system that reflects man’s knowledge and experience in the form of “quanta” of knowledge; which is only partially verbalized by language in the form of its meaning, and contains a significant proportion of non-verbal information”.²

One of the universal concepts that has been extensively studied is the concept DISEASE, which is not only researched by linguists³, but also by professionals from various fields, including medicine⁴, cultural studies⁵, and philosophy⁶, among others.

In cognitive linguistics, it has long been a truism that concepts are verbalised in a language using keywords. For example, the concept DISEASE in English is verbalised by the words disease, illness, sickness, morbidity, infirmity, ailment, indisposition, complaint, disorder, malady, and badness, which denote a person's different physical or mental states. Such keywords with the meaning ‘disease’ in ancient Greek are ἡ νόσος/ τὸ νόσημα, ἡ ἀρρωστία/τὸ ἀρρώστημα, ἡ ἀσθένεια, which denoting the disease in general, differed somewhat in meaning, naming its various states, as well as ἡ μανία for mental disorder⁷. It is worth to say that in ancient Greek, the

¹ E. Margolis, S. Laurence, *Concepts*. Encyclopedia of Language and Linguistics, Amsterdam, Elsevier, 2006, p. 817.

² E.S. Kubryakova, *Concept. Conceptualization*. E. S. Kubryakova, V. Z. Demyankov al. The short dictionary of cognitive terms, Moskow, MGU, 1996, p.90. Cf.: “an operative unit of consciousness’ corresponding to a particular sign” (L. Manerko, *Concept understanding in cognitive linguistics and cognitive terminology science*. Languages for Special Purposes in a Multilingual, Transcultural World. Proceedings of the 19th European Symposium on Languages for Special Purposes, Vienna, University of Vienna, 2014, p. 471).

³ Z. Dubinets, *The concept of "disease" in the linguistic picture of the world of Ukrainians and Russians*. Bulletin of Lviv University, Philological series, Lviv, no 2, 2017, pp. 366-375.; O. Labenko, *The concept of DISEASE in Ukrainian, English and French: ethnolinguistic perspective*, Lviv Philological Journal, no 4, 2018, pp. 49-54.; Yu. Rozhkov, A.Syrotin, *Verbalization of the concepts of disease and animal disease in English*. Cogito. Multidisciplinary research Journal, vol. 13, no 4, 2021, pp. 224-233.

⁴ C. Helman, *Disease versus illness in general practice*. The Journal of the Royal College of General Practitioners, vol. 31, 1981, pp. 548-552.

⁵ L.Eisenberg, *Disease and illness. Distinctions between professional and popular ideas of sickness*. Culture, Medicine and Psychiatry, vol.1, 1977, pp. 9–23; A. Kleinman, *Patients and healers in the context of culture: An exploration of the Borderland between Anthropology*. Los-Angeles: University of California Press, 1980.

⁶ H. Fabrega, *Concepts of disease: Logical features and social implications*. Perspectives in Biology and Medicine, vol. 15, 1972, pp. 617-621; K.M. Boyd, *Disease, illness, sickness, health, healing and wholeness: exploring some elusive concepts*. Medical humanities, vol. 26, no. 1, 2000, pp. 9-17.

⁷ It is worth noting that in the minds of the ancient Greeks, the word μανία and its derivatives did not have a priori negative connotations, denoting any deviation from the

word πάθος (pathos) was also used with a similar meaning. As Galen notes, “The ancients used the word ‘pathos’ as well as the terms ‘ἄρρωστία’ (arrhōstia) and ‘ἀσθένεια’ (astheneia) to refer to a disease, as discussed in treatises on medical vocabulary” (Galen, *De methodo* 10, p. 91, 7-14).

Speaking about the key lexemes-verbalizers of the concept DISEASE in ancient Greek, it should be noted at once that, unlike to modern languages, in explanatory dictionaries the meaning of such lexemes are explained (cf. the definitions of the above-mentioned English words for disease in the Oxford English Dictionary⁸), we do not know the exact sense that the ancient Greeks put into them. Lexicographical sources point to synonymy (full or partial) of the first three words, cf. νόσος - sickness, disease; ἄρρωστία - weakness, sickness; ἀρρώστημα - illness, sickness; ἀσθένεια - want of strength, weakness, disease, sickness⁹. They are used in a similar sense in Galen's treatises¹⁰. It is worth noting that glossaries give νόσος and ἄρρωστία as equivalents of the Latin ‘morbus’¹¹.

Based on the scanty evidence, we can conclude that νόσος (νόσημα) and ἄρρωστία (ἀρρώστημα) differed in terms of ‘strength’ and ‘duration’: ἀρρώστημα ... ἐστὶ νόσημα μετὰ ἀσθενείας (Diog. Laert. VII, 115) “infirmity is meant disease accompanied by weakness”; ἄρρωστία σημαίνει μὲν πολλαχοῦ τὴν νόσον, ἀλλὰ καὶ διαφέρει, ὅτι ἢ μὲν νόσος ἐστὶ καὶ μακρὰ καὶ ὀλιγοχρόνιος, ἢ δὲ ἄρρωστία τὴν μακροχρόνιον (Phryn. Praep. soph. 10 B) “affliction (ἀρρωστία) often denotes disease (νόσον), but it also differs because disease is long and short-lived, and affliction is long-lasting”. Ammonius also points to a partial difference in meaning: ἀρρωστεῖν τοῦ νοσεῖν διαφέρει. ἀρρωστεῖ μὲν γὰρ ὁ καχεκτῶν τῷ σώματι, νοσεῖ δὲ ὁ κλινήρης (Ammon. Diff. 1, 79) “To be unwell’ (ἀρρωστεῖν) is different from “to be ill” (νοσεῖν), because the unwell are physically weak, while the ill are bedridden.”

A similar characterization is also found in Galen and his followers, who regarded powerlessness as a common feature of all disease states (πάθη): ... ἀσθένεια- κοινὴ ... κατὰ πάντα τὰ πάθη...(Gal. *De placitis* 4, 6, 14) “powerlessness is common ... to all diseases”; ἀρρώστημα ἐστὶ νόσημα

usual state of consciousness, including in a positive way. Cf. Pl. *Phdr.* 244 a-b: ...τὰ μέγιστα τῶν ἀγαθῶν ἡμῖν γίνεταί διὰ μανίας, θεῖα μὲντοι δόσει διδομένης τῶν παλαιῶν ... οὐκ αἰσχρὸν ἠγοῦντο οὐδὲ ὄνειδος μανίαν ‘...the greatest of blessings come to us through madness, when it is sent as a gift of the gods...those men of old ... thought that madness was neither shameful nor disgraceful’ (trans. H. N. Fowler).

⁸ *Oxford English Dictionary (OED)*. Retrieved from URL:

<https://www.oed.com/?tl=true>

⁹ H. G. Liddel, R. Scott, *A Greek-English Lexicon*. Oxford, Clarendon Press, 1983, s.v.

¹⁰ R. J. Durling, *A Dictionary of Medical Terms in Galen*, Leiden, Brill, 1993 s.v.

¹¹ G. Goetz, *Thesaurus glossarum emendatarum. Pars prior*. Lipsiae, B. G. Teubner, 1899, p. 710.

ἐγκεχροισμένον μετ' ἀσθενείας πλείονος. ἢ ἀρρώστημά ἐστι νόσημα ... ἐλαττοῦν τὴν δύναμιν (Ps.-Gal. Gal. Definitions 19, p. 390, 16-18) “sickness (ἀρρώστημα) is a prolonged illness (νόσημα) with greater impotence or sickness is an illness... that reduces strength” (cf. τὰ δὲ νοσήματα μετ' ἀσθενείας συμβαίνοντα ἀρρώστηματα καλεῖσθαι (Stob. Ecl. II, 93, 1) “diseases (νοσήματα) accompanied by weakness are called infirmities (ἀρρώστηματα)”).

According to G. Babiniotis, the terms ἀρρώστια (illness) and ἀσθένεια (disease) primarily denote long-term disabilities and weaknesses. The term νόσος (disease) is often used interchangeably with νόσημα (pathological condition) and can refer to both acute and chronic health issues¹².

In view of this complexity of the concept DISEASE¹³, it is reasonable to consider it as a macro-concept that encompasses various sub-concepts. I think that the ancient Greek language identifies the following sub-concepts: ΝΟΣΟΣ (general poor health influenced by negative factors on human being), ΑΣΘΕΝΕΙΑ (lack of strength)¹⁴, and ΜΑΝΙΑ (mental inadequacy).

The research of key lexemes of this concept can be undertaken by examining their paradigmatic and syntagmatic relationships, as well as considering their etymology and word formation.

This article aims to analyze and to model the propositional-frame structure of the word-formation cluster centred around the term νόσος from a cognitive perspective.

The selection of derivatives from the above-mentioned noun as the focus of study is based on several key reasons: 1) The primary meaning of 'disease' is fundamental to this lexeme, this denotative meaning preserving in its derivatives; 2) The terms νόσος and its variant νόσημα are the most commonly used among the words denoting disease as an abnormal state; 3) The word family derived from this noun is the most extensive; 4) Historically, νόσος (the Homeric νοῦσος) belongs to the oldest layer of the lexicon.

Methods. Within the cognitive approach, linguists focus on the study of derivatives. These derivatives do not only serve as a database that organizes a significant amount of information but also provide speakers

¹² Μπαμπινιώτης, Γ., *Λέξικο της νέας ελληνικής γλώσσας*, Αθήνα, Κέντρο λεξικολογίας 2002, p. 285.

¹³ J. Amzat, O. Razum, *Medical Sociology in Africa*, Cham, Springer, 2014, p. 21, 26.

¹⁴ In addition to the noun ἀσθένεια and its derivatives, the sub-concept is also expressed through words derived from the stem ἀρρωστ-. The term ΑΣΘΕΝΕΙΑ is used to name this sub-concept due to the higher frequency of derivatives from the ἀσθεν- stem.

with frameworks to integrate specific knowledge structures with word-formation patterns and mechanisms for modelling word formation¹⁵.

Researchers concentrate their attention on both individual derivatives and complex word formation units—including various types and nests of word formation—as tools for linguistically representing conceptual formations that emerge from our cognition and evaluation of the world. By combining words that share a common root, and thus a common semantic and formal component, researchers can effectively illustrate how word formation contributes to the processes of naming, as well as the broader processes of conceptualization and categorization of our surroundings and our place within it, using the national language¹⁶.

Conceptual derivation is a cognitive process in which the combination of concepts generates new knowledge structures. The concepts that emerge from cognitive activities are expressed in language, becoming integral to the conceptual system. However, these concepts also maintain a derivational connection to the original structures, serving as a foundation for further development of the system¹⁷.

The relationships between derivatives within the same family are reflected in the intentional use of common root words in a text and the creation of new words. Thus, the sequence and chronology of derivative word formation are not fundamentally significant.

Each common root lexeme within the word-formation continuum represents new cultural information, contributing to the establishment of a cohesive word-formation network (derivational framework). This framework forms a part of the linguistic picture of the world, where each fragment represents a word-formation family of shared root units. It reflects the semantic and cultural trends and directions in the development of all language units relevant to culture and society, considering their national, and ethnic significance, as well as mental value.

According to O. Selivanova, "the process of conceptual derivation ensures the combination of concepts into a conceptual structure that underlies the semantics of the derived word. This structure resembles a sentence, where each common root word in speech and thought interacts with another word in the nest, reflecting isomorphic relationships among

¹⁵ E.S. Kubryakova, *Language and knowledge: on the way of acquisition of knowledge about language. Parts of speech from the cognitive point of view*, Moskow, Yazyki slavyanskoy kultury, 2004, p. 393.

¹⁶ E.A. Karpilovskaya, *The nests in systematic organization of lexicon: possibilities of modelling and cross-linguistic comparison*. Researches on Slavic languages, vol. 12, 2007, p. 229.

¹⁷ O.O. Koliadenko, *Propositional-frame analysis of word-building paradigm of representative lexeme of the concept "FEAR"*. Scientific transactions of the National University of Ostroh Academy, series "Philology", vol. 13, 2010, p. 318.

the components of the denotative situation. A complete description of these potentially typical role relations between common root allows us to view the nest as a complex situation or frame"¹⁸.

In this article, the key terms used in the meta-language of description are frame, slot, propositional structure, and proposition (definitions are provided below). These terms represent the most general forms of knowledge representation and illustrate the processes of derivation and nomination of derived words. Derivatives play a significant role in relevant describing of the knowledge that individuals rely on when creating them. This knowledge serves as a carrier of information that is important to a specific socio-cultural community.

M. Minsky describes a frame as a data structure used to represent a stereotyped situation conceptualized as a network of nodes or relations. The "top levels" of a frame are fixed and denote aspects that are always true about the assumed situation"¹⁹ [Minsky 1979: 1].

As Ch. Fillmore states, the lexical semantics of a word conveys a specific situation that is related to a frame by using a particular 'perspective' or focusing on its elements. Each frame includes various terminals that connect to other frames. The upper levels of a frame, known as its core, correspond to representations that are unique to a given situation²⁰.

A key component of a frame is a slot (referred to as a 'terminal' in Minsky's terminology) that is focused on specifying knowledge by filling it with 'specific instances or data'²¹. These slots, in turn, create propositional schemes based on predication, which consists of a predicate along with its actants. For instance, the term 'tenderfoot', meaning 'someone who has just started doing something,' corresponds to the proposition 'a person who is characterized by an organ.' This is an example of the propositional scheme 'subject-predicate-object'. In this case, the predicate is 'to start doing,' while the actants are 'someone' (subject) and 'foot' (object).

Filling the cells of the schemes mentioned above with a base word or its derivatives creates a specific proposition. This forms a scheme of elementary situations.²², representing a mental framework that exists in the

¹⁸ O. Selivanova, *Modern linguistics. Terminological encyclopedia*, Poltava, Dovkillya-K, 2006, p. 615.

¹⁹ M. Minsky, *Framework for Representing Knowledge*. Frame conceptions and texts understanding, Berlin; New York, de Gruyter, 1979, p. 1.

²⁰ Ch. J. Fillmore, *An Alternative to Checklist Theories of Meaning*. Proceedings of the First Annual Meeting of the Berkeley Linguistics Society, Berkeley, California, Berkeley Linguistics Society, 1975, p. 124.

²¹ M. Minsky, *Op. cit.*, p.1.

²² Cf. "Propositions are the linguistic meanings of the sentences we utter or write down, they are the contents of our sayings when we utter or write down those sentences,

mind of a language user. The frame model connects these situations into a cohesive network²³. The primary semantic function of a proposition is its ability to describe a "situation" or a "state of affairs," which are fragments of reality²⁴. A frame can encompass one or more propositions. Within the context of word formation, I consider a proposition as the fundamental complex unit at the word-formation level of a language—a nest of cognates. A proposition serves as the basis for isolating a situation within a frame.

Humans are born with an innate mechanism for abstract categories. These categories can either be immediately inherent to cognition or acquired in the early years of life, but they are fundamentally innate to all modern humans²⁵. Such categories are utilized in propositional structures, which, according to W. Chafe²⁶, involve selecting objects from events and situations and assigning syntactic roles to these objects. In the process of categorizing the world, propositional structures guide human thought towards the use of verbal hints (propositions). The organization of the derivational paradigm resembles the structure of a frame: derivational processes aim to fill the positions within this frame. Consequently, the products of derivation, known as derivational units, are grouped accordingly. The cognates indicate the positions of the subject, predicate, object, locative, and other elements relevant to the corresponding proposition.

Such approach to studying a concept is represented by a word formation structure—where the top element is the name of the concept—will enable us to reproduce the intra-systemic relationships between the components (or slots) of its frame structure. It will also help us to determine the directions in which the creation of derivative units verbalize the concept.

Material. This study was conducted by using authoritative dictionaries of the ancient Greek language²⁷. Additionally, a corpus of ancient Greek texts from the Perseus and Thesaurus Linguae Graecae databases was used.

and they are the contents of our thoughts" (S. Crawford, (2006). *Proposition*. Encyclopedia of Language and Linguistics, vol. 10, Amsterdam, Elsevier, 2006, p. 162).

²³ M.S. Kosyreva, *The categories of propositional analysis as forerunner and basis of frame modelling in derivatology*. Modern problems of science and education, vol. 6, 2008, pp. 169–173; E.S. Kubryakova, *Language and knowledge: on the way of acquisition of knowledge about language. Parts of speech from the cognitive point of view*, Moskow, Yazyki slavyanskoy kultury, 2004.

²⁴ L. Wittgenstein, *Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus*. London: Kegan Paul, Trench, Trubner & Co, 1922, p. 39.

²⁵ N. Chomsky, *Language and Mind*. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2006.

²⁶ W. Chafe, *The Recall and Verbalization of Past Experience*. Current issues in linguistic theory, Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 1977, pp. 215-246.

²⁷ H.G. Liddel, R. Scott, *op. cit.*; F. Montanari, *The Brill Dictionary of Ancient Greek*, Leiden, Brill, 2015; J. Diggle, *The Cambridge Greek Lexicon*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2021.

Results of the Study. Before proceeding to model the propositional-frame structure of the verbalization of the sub-concept ΝΟΣΟΣ, it is important to characterize the word-formation network that develops around the base νοσ-.

The lexeme νόσος, which occupies the top position in this word-formation network, does not have a specific etymology. Based on the epic and Ionic form νοῦσος, the proposed etymon *νοσφοσ has been suggested²⁸. However, according to J. Wackernagel²⁹ νοῦσος may be incorrect spelling of νόσος and might instead represent the original form *νόσσοσ. Additionally, A. Willi considers the etymon to be the composite *n-osu-os, meaning 'devoid of health', derived from *(h₁)osu-, which means 'health'³⁰.

As the central element of the word-formation network, the lexeme νόσος is translated as 'sickness, disease, plague; distress, anguish; bane, mischief'³¹, or the root νοσ-, referred to as a 'morphologies metaconcept' (a term used by O. Garmash)³², serves as the source for several derivatives. This includes a total of 51 units, representing nouns, adjectives, verbs, and adverbs, which are in Table 1.

Table 1. The word-formation nest with the top 'νόσος'

Noun	Adjective	Verb	Adverb
ἀνοσία «freedom from sickness», νόσανσις, νόσωσις «falling sick», νοσερότης «infirmities», νόσευμα, νόσημα, νοσήμη «sickness,	ἄνοσος «without sickness, healthy», ἐπινοσος «unhealthy», νοσακερός «liable to sickness, sickly», νοσερός (νοσηρός) «diseased,	νοσάζω «to be ill; produce sickness», νοσεύομαι «to be sickly», νοσεῖω «to be sick», νοσηλεύω	ἀνόσως 'healthy', ἐπινόσως 'like one who is sick', νοσερῶς 'unhealthy', νοσημὰ τικῶς 'morbidly',

²⁸ H. Frisk, *Griechisches etymologisches Wörterbuch. 2: Kr – Omega*. Heidelberg, Winter, 2006, p. 324; R. Beekes, *Etymological dictionary of Greek*. Leiden, Brill, 2010, p. 1024.

²⁹ J. Wackernagel, *Sprachliche Untersuchungen zu Homer*. Göttingen, Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1916, p.86.

³⁰ A. Willi, *Nόσος and ὁσίη: etymological and sociocultural observations on the concepts of disease and divine (dis)favour in ancient Greece*. The Journal of Hellenic studies, vol. 128, 2008, pp. 153 – 171.

³¹ H. G. Liddel, R. Scott, *op. cit.*, s. v.

³² "Morphological metaconcept is a unit of metacognition, a constituent of the metacognitive level of the lingvo-mental setting and has such characteristics as: universality, dynamism, polarity, fractal determinacy, clustering, variability, bignerativity and reproducibility; consists of verbocentric, mentocentric and metacentric information" (O.L. Garmash, *English morphological metaconcepts in the processes of conceptual derivation (on the material of lingual innovations late XX – early XXI century)*). Thesis for the Doctoral Degree in Philosophy. Odesa, I. I. Mechnikov National University, 2017, p. 5).

<p><i>disease</i>», νοσημάτιον «<i>little disease</i>», νοσηλεία «<i>care of the sick, nursing; sickness which needs tending</i>», νοσοκομείον «<i>infirmary, hospital</i>», νοσοκομία «<i>care of the sick</i>», νοσοκόμος «<i>sick-nurse</i>», νοσοτροφία «<i>nursing of disease</i>», νουσολύτης «<i>freeing from illness</i>» (Paean's epithet)</p>	<p><i>unhealthy</i>», νοσήλιος, νοσηλός, νοσηματικός «<i>of /for sickness, morbid, diseased</i>», νοσηματώδης, νοσώδης «<i>sickly, ailing, unwholesome, pestilential</i>», νοσητήριος «<i>unhealthy</i>», νοσηφόρος «<i>disease-bringing</i>», νοσογνωμονικός «<i>skilled in judging of diseases by their symptoms</i>», νοσοεργός, νοσοποιός «<i>causing sickness</i>», νοσόθυμος «<i>sick at heart</i>», νοσοβαρής «<i>caused by grievous disease</i>», νοσομελής «<i>with diseased limbs</i>», νουσαχθής «<i>affected with disease</i>», παυσίνοσος «<i>curing sickness</i>», Νόσιος «<i>Healer</i>» (Zeus' epithet)</p>	<p>νοσοκομέω «<i>tend a sick person</i>», νοσιζω «<i>make sick</i>», νοσολογέω «<i>explain a disease</i>», νοσοποιέω «<i>cause sickness</i>», νοσοτυφέω «<i>to be ostentatious in sickness</i>», ἐπινοσέω «<i>to be ill after</i>», ἐκνοσηλεύω «<i>cure completely</i>»</p>	<p>νοσηματωδῶς, νοσωδῶς «<i>unwholesome</i></p>
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Researchers studying word-formation processes typically distinguish between two main methods: derivation and word formation. Derivation refers to creating new words by adding affixes, while word formation involves combining two words or roots to form a new word³³. However, since both processes result in the creation of new words and are often

³³ A. Ralli, *Compounding versus derivation*. Cross-Disciplinary Issues in Compounding, Amsterdam, John Benjamins, 2010, p. 57. As R. Dearmond states "the term "derivation" is used in linguistics in two distinct ways. In one sense, it refers to the historical or diachronic development of a word, whether from an earlier form or through the addition of an affix to an existing word. In the second sense, derivation describes the synchronous formation of a word based on another word that is considered to "underlie" it" (R.C. Dearmond, *The Concept of Word Derivation*. *Lingua*, vol. 22, 1969, p. 329).

interconnected, we will treat them as part of a single derivation process, in line with the findings of A. Wouters and P. Swiggers³⁴.

Based on their formation methods, derivatives from the mentioned root can be categorized into several groups: those formed with prefixes, those formed with suffixes, and those created through compounding stems (Table 2). Among these groups, prefix formations are the least common, accounting for only 4 lexemes (8%). Meanwhile, suffixation is more prevalent, comprising 29 lexemes (57%), and stem formation represents a significant group as well, with 18 lexemes (35%).

Table 2. Word-formation types of derivatives from the root νοσ-

Prefixation	Suffixation	Compounding
ἄνοσος, ἐπίνοσος, ἐπινοσέω, ἐκνοσηλεύω	ἀνοσία, νόσανσις, νόσωσις, νοσερότης, νοσήμη, νόσευμα, νόσημα, νοσημάτιον, νοσηλεία, νοσακερός, νοσερός (νοσηρός), νοσήλιος, νοσηλός, νοσηματικός, νοσηματώδης, νοσώδης, νοσητήριος, Νόσιος, ἀνόσως, ἐπινόσως, νοσερῶς, νοσηματικῶς, νοσηματωδῶς, νοσωδῶς, νοσέω, νοσάζω, νοσιζω, νοσεύομαι, νοσηλεύω	νοσοκομεῖον, νοσοκομία, νοσοκόμος, νοσοτροφία, νοσολύτης, νοσηφόρος, νοσογνωμονικός, νοσοεργός, νοσοποιός, νοσόθυμος, νοσοβαρής, νοσομελής, νοσοαχθής, παυσίνοσος, νοσοκομέω, νοσολογέω, νοσοποιέω, νοσοτυφέω,

The lexemes derived from the root "νοσ-" belong to various chronological layers. Some of these, such as ἄνοσος, νόσημα, νοσηλεία, νοσοτροφία, and νοσώδης, can be traced back to authors like Homer, the tragedians, Herodotus, and Plato. In contrast, other terms—such as ἐπίνοσος, νοσηματώδης, νοσηματικός, and νοσακερός—emerged starting with Aristotle. Typically, compound words are dated to the Hellenistic-Roman period. However, as previously mentioned, the chronology and sequence of derivative formation are not crucial for our analysis.

The propositional-frame analysis will enable us to reconstruct the intra-systemic connections between the components (slots) of the frame structure within the word formation nest centred on the term νόσος. This approach will help us to identify the directions according to which derivational units are created. Following the widely accepted terminology³⁵, we will differentiate the following propositional sides:

- Subject (S) - the performer of the action

³⁴ A. Wouters, P. Swiggers, *Word Formation (Derivation, Compounding)*. Encyclopedia of Ancient Greek Language and Linguistics, vol. 3, Leiden, Brill, 2013, p. 521.

³⁵ O.O. Koliadenko, *Op. cit.*, p. 321; O. Oleksenko, *Propositional analysis as a method of modelling of word-building nest*. Grammatical Studies, vol. 2, Vinnytsia, DonNU, 2016, p. 9

- Object (O) - the object of the action
- Predicate (P) - the action or state inherent to the subject
- Locus (L) - the location where the action occurs
- Tempus (T) - the time when the action takes place
- Modus (M) - how the action is performed
- Result (R) - the consequences of the action
- Conjunctive (C) - a conditional unit symbolizing the overall situation
- Attribute (At) - an element that indicates a participant in the situation through a feature

In view of specifics of the word-formation nest we are studying, we will also include the position of state (St). However, the position of tool (I) - representing the instrument used in the action - is not present within this particular nest.

The meanings of the derivational units that comprise the studied word "nest" convey knowledge about the specific situation represented within the nest. The connections between the components of this situation are quite logical. Disease, as a pathological condition of the organism, is a response to a negative external influence (νοσίζω, νοσοποιέω). Therefore, in objective reality, there is someone or something that causes the disease (νοσοεργός, νοσοποιός) or helps eliminate it (νοσοκόμος, νουσολύτης, παυσίνοσος). The experiencer (whether being or non-being) is considered the bearer of the trait (νοσερός, νοσήλιος, νουσαχθής), and the object affected by the disease is represented by (νοσόθυμος, νουσομελής).

The frame structure of the nest, with "νόσος" as the central concept, is complex. Within it, we can identify seven slots represented by different propositional schemes (PropS) and, consequently, various propositions (Prop).

Slot 1: Lack of health

PropS: P (νοσέω, έπινοσέω³⁶ νοσάζω³⁷) — At (νοσερός/νοσηρός, νοσητήριος, νουσαχθής) — M (νοσερῶς/νοσηρῶς) — St (νόσος, νόσευμα, νόσημα, νοσήμη) — K (νόσανσις, νόσωσις).

Prop: 'Being in a state of illnesses.'

Slot 2: Intensity.

PropS: St_p³⁸ (νόσος, νόσευμα, νόσημα, νοσήμη) — St_{sec} (νοσερότης, νοσημάτιον) — At (νοσητήριος, νουσοβαρής)

Prop: 'The state is named by its intensity.'

³⁶ The verb έπινοσέω, meaning 'to be ill after,' combines the roles of 'predicate' (P) and 'time' (T).

³⁷ νοσάζω₁ 'to be ill'

³⁸ The abbreviations "St_p" and "St_{sec}" denote primary and secondary state, respectively.

The distinctive feature of this propositional structure is the lack of a predicate, since the scalar nature of the derivatives does not imply any action that would weaken the meaning of the source lexeme.

Slot 3. Sickness.

PropS: P (νοσεύομαι) – At (ἐπίνοσος, νοσακερός³⁹, νοσήλιος, νοσηλός, νοσηματικός) – M (ἐπινόσως, νοσηματικῶς).

Prop: 'a sign characterising a predisposition to disease'.

Slot 4. Pathological condition of an organ.

PropS: O (θυμός, μέλος) – P (νοσέω, νοσάζω₁) – At (νοσόθυμος, νοσομελής).

Prop: 'An object characterised by a state of illness'.

Slot 5. Causation.

PropS: P (νοσιζω, νοσοποιέω, νοσάζω₂) – At (νοσηματώδης, νοσώδης, νοσηφόρος, νοσοεργός, νοσοποιός) – M (νοσηματωδῶς, νοσωδῶς) – R (νόσος, νόσευμα, νόσημα, νοσήμη) – K (νόσανσις, νόσωσις).

Prop: 'That which causes disease'.

Similarly to slot 1, the subject in this sentence structure can be a substantive participles or adjectives.

Slot 6. Elimination of disease.

PropS: S (νοσοκόμος, νουσολύτης, Νόσιος) – P ((ἐκ)νοσηλεύω, νοσοκομέω) – At (παυσίνοσος) – L (νοσοκομεῖον) – R (ἀνοσία, ἄνοσος) – M (ἀνόσως) – K (νοσηλεία, νοσοκομία, νοσοτροφία).

Prop: 'The one who helps to get rid of the disease'.

Slot 7. Diagnosis of an illness.

PropS: P (νοσολογέω) – At (νοσογνωμονικός).

Prop: the ability to recognise or explain an illness.

A characteristic feature of most propositional structures (except for the one represented in slot 6) is the absence of derivatives from the root "νοσ-" to indicate the subject. This role can be filled by a substantivated participle. For example, ὁ ... νοσῶν (S) εἰς πολλὰ καὶ φαρμάκων καὶ χειρουργίας καὶ διαίτης δεόμενος εἰς οὐδὲν δεῖται γυμνασίων, ὁ δ' ὑγιαίνων ἀκριβῶς γυμνασίων μὲν χρήζει καὶ διαίτης τινός, οὔτε δὲ φαρμάκων οὔτε χειρουργίας προσδεῖται (Gal. Thrasyb. 34)"...a patient who needs a lot of medicine, surgery, and diet does not require gymnastics at all; conversely, a healthy person undoubtedly engages in gymnastics and follows some form of diet but needs neither medicine nor surgery."

Additionally, it is important to note that adjectives derived from "νοσ-" are not found in the subject function.

³⁹ νοσακερός₁ 'liable to sickness'

The same lexemes can serve different roles in a proposition depending on its context. For instance, in the first position (slot 1), the words νόσος, νόσευμα, νόσημα, and νοσήμη represent a state, while in the fifth position (slot 5), they indicate a result.

Conclusions. The analysis of the derivatives associated with the term "νόσος" reveals that there are both semantic and word-formation relationships among them within its context. All derivatives maintain a strong semantic connection to the root lexeme, gradually linking their meanings to create a logically structured representation of the linguistic worldview. The proposed analysis of the word-formation nest with the top "ΝΟΣΟΣ" allows us to identify seven slots in its frame structure: lack of health, intensity, soreness, pathological state of the organ, causation, eliminating disease, and diagnosis. These slots reflect the gradual progression of a frame that shows the occurrence of a disease, its presence, and elimination, while also illustrating the formation of derivative units.

Representing the analyzed word-formation nest as a frame enables us to identify its structural components: slots, propositional schemes, and propositions. The most productive slots — those most represented by elements of propositional schemes and their corresponding lexemes — are slots 1, 5, and 6, leading us to consider them as core components. In contrast to slot 7 has the fewest elements and thus occupies a peripheral position. Slots 2 - 4 hold an intermediate status, each represented by three elements of propositional schemes and approximately the same number of lexemes. The analysis established that in the vast majority of slots (with the exception of slot 2) the propositional scheme 'Predicate — Attribute' is implemented. Depending on the semantics of the lexemes it can be extended with other elements such as Modus, Object, Conjunction etc. The different times of derivatives' emergence and their diversity demonstrate the progressive development of knowledge from elementary to complex as well as visualise different ways of semantic derivation and nomination.

The treating of the word formation "nest" as a frame is quite perspective. This approach offers a clear categorization and semantic organization of linguistic and cultural knowledge regarding base and derivative words. It enables to assess the derivational potential of a word, which largely depends on how relevant the concepts and realities represented by the base words and their derivatives are relevant to native speakers.

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